

The role of alternative proteins and future foods in sustainable and contextually-adapted flexitarian diets

Ashley Green^{1,2*}, Christoph Blatmann^{1,3}, Canxi Chen¹, Alexander Mathys^{1*}

*These authors share corresponding authorship

¹ ETH Zurich, Institute of Food, Nutrition and Health, Laboratory of Sustainable Food Processing, Schmelzbergstrasse 9, Zurich, 8092, Switzerland

² Agroscope, Life Cycle Assessment Research Group, Zurich, Switzerland, 191 Reckenholzstrasse 8046

³ Bühler AG, Gupfenstrasse 5, 9240 Uzwil, Switzerland

*Corresponding authors

Email addresses: ashley.green@hest.ethz.ch; alexander.mathys@hest.ethz.ch

This is an earlier copy. To see the final version refer to: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2022.03.026>

Abstract

Background: Devising contextually-adapted and **sustainable flexitarian diets** that integrate **alternative proteins and future foods** can support sustainable food systems.

Scope and approach: In this commentary, we critically evaluate the role of alternative proteins and future foods (i.e., microalgae, insects, fungi, cultured meat, and plant-based meat) with respect to tradeoffs with animal- and plant- sourced foods in future flexitarian diets. We focus on four key sustainability dimensions including **environmental impacts**, **nutrition/health**, **animal welfare**, and **antibiotic use**. We further explore the differentiated role of meat products (e.g., chicken vs. beef), in addition to production practices that simultaneously increase nutrient contents while decreasing environmental impacts. Finally, we illustrate why and how context-specific conditions; namely, environmental, nutritional/health, access, culture, and knowledge boundaries, should be considered when developing these diets.

Key findings and conclusions: The role of alternative proteins in sustainable flexitarian diets is highly variable depending on the food item and production method (e.g., feed substrate, processing technology). Furthermore, environmental tradeoffs exist (e.g., low land use but high energy demand) as well as nutritional gaps including a lack of certainty regarding nutritional equivalency claims from future foods when compared to their contemporary counterparts. Moreover, strong uncertainties around nutrient absorption (e.g., bioavailability) and activity in the body exist. Animal welfare and antibiotic use concerns have promise to be strongly mitigated with the introduction of alternative proteins. Finally, more standardized and robust sustainability assessments are needed. Overall, future foods hold promise to support sustainable and contextually-adapted flexitarian diets, but significant work and understanding is still needed.

Keywords: sustainable flexitarian diets, alternative proteins/ future foods, nutrition, environmental impacts, animal welfare, antibiotic use

Accepted

1. Introduction

The science is clear; society must shift toward more plant-based diets, to protect against environmental degradation. Even with an immediate halt in fossil fuel emissions, ignoring the food system would mean a breach of the 1.5°C climate change target and an acceptance of the climatic impacts (Clark et al., 2020). The environmental and nutritional dimensions of our food system are inextricably interlinked (Green et al., 2021; Willett et al., 2019); consequently, we must reduce environmental burdens while alleviating burdens of malnutrition (e.g., micronutrient deficiencies), which affect billions of people across all income levels. Currently, there is no common consensus on how this aforementioned ‘diet shift’ is defined nor on how we can accomplish it in a meaningful manner and how doing so will vary depending on context-specific situations., (e.g., geographical-region, gender, or income). While certain high-level dietary analyses offer a useful starting point, until country guidelines are adopted (inclusive of context-specificities and more targeted roadmaps), actions might be limited. Moreover, as alternative proteins and future foods (AP-FF) enter the market, addressing how they can contribute to this diet shift is a crucial gap to explore in support of making meaningful differences with our dietary choices. Tangentially, optimizing production and processing practices to reduce environmental impacts while improving nutritional profiles is an overlooked but prime source of opportunity for developing more robust sustainable diets (Green et al., 2020).

We focus on five categories of AP-FF, chosen for their high relevance or widely-discussed potential as meat alternatives. While the market for AP-FF is projected to reach \$290 billion by 2035; AP-FF only comprised 2% of the total animal protein market in 2020 (Morach et al., 2021). The food groups include alternative proteins such as (i) plant-based meat substitutes sold as direct replacements for meat (e.g., plant-based burgers or chicken— not tofu) and (ii) fungi-based products (i.e., mycoprotein); as well as future foods including (iii) microalgae (i.e., not seaweed which is a macroalgae), (iv) insects, and (v) cultured meat. Plant-based meat substitutes are the most commercially-available AP-FF. They are commonly made of soy and pea protein isolates or concentrates, due to their beneficial protein functionalities. Microalgae such as single cellular organisms like cyanobacteria (e.g., *Spirulina*) and green microalgae (e.g., *Chlorella*) and insect-based products are also commercially available but limited on a wide-scale. Insects, harvested from the natural environment, are consumed in many nations (Tang et al., 2019), and now industrial-scale production is being adopted. Fungi-based products like mycoprotein, often produced via fermentation, are also available in niche markets. Cultured meat (also referred to as lab-grown or cellular meat), on the other hand, is only commercially available as a hybrid product in limited markets such as Singapore [e.g., there is a 70% cultured chicken product that is supplemented with plant-protein to add structure (Dolgin, 2020)].

Understanding how to make future flexitarian diets more sustainable is a pertinent endeavor because: (i) previous studies have argued for the incorporation of small meat portions, citing reasons of nutrition and livelihoods and (ii) meat consumption is expected to increase 14% by 2030 (OECD/FAO, 2021). To support this dietary development, this commentary aims to: (i) elucidate the need to define future flexitarian diets; (ii) evaluate sustainability dimensions (i.e., environment, nutrition/health, animal welfare, and antibiotic overuse) of AP-FF as well as the differentiated role of

41 products within the meat group (e.g., chicken versus beef); (iii) illustrate the pertinent role of
42 production-based interventions; and finally, (iv) exemplify the need to integrate context-specific
43 boundaries (i.e., financial and physical access, nutritional, cultural, and environmental) when defining
44 flexitarian diets.

45 **2. Challenges in defining sustainable and future flexitarian diets**

46 While dietary patterns such as veganism or vegetarianism have clear definitions; historically, the
47 characterization of flexitarian diets within sustainability boundaries remains ambiguous. Broadly,
48 flexitarianism is a plant-based diet inclusive of a small meat portion; this ‘portion,’ however, is loosely
49 defined. Certain diets include all meat types but with a clear (e.g., 1x/week, 1x/month, ‘meatless-
50 Mondays’) or unclear (e.g., moderate-intake) threshold, while others exclude red meat but include fish
51 and chicken. The recent EAT-Lancet report proposed a flexitarian diet to stay within planetary
52 boundaries; however, while it provides useful recommendations at a broad scale, more work is needed
53 before this information is actionable at national scales. For example, recent studies have signaled the
54 diet inadequately addresses food security (Vaidyanathan, 2021), water use (Tuninetti et al., 2022),
55 potential nutrient adequacy (Vaidyanathan, 2021), circularity (van Selm et al., 2022), and affordability
56 (Hirvonen et al., 2020a) at more granular scales. Lastly, there is a need to define flexitarian diets with
57 the incorporation of AP-FF, which has been explored in a siloed and limited manner.

58 The risk with such an ill-defined flexitarian term is unknowingly overshooting environmental
59 boundaries when trying to eat enough meat to satisfy nutrient requirements. In practice, flexitarians
60 consume different amounts and types of meat (Malek & Umberger, 2021) and certain flexitarians do
61 not drastically deviate from their previous meat eating habits (Dagevos, 2021). Relatedly, studies have
62 suggested it is unclear if people reduce their meat consumption when adopting meat substitutes
63 (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017). Without clear guidance, consumer’s choices can be ineffective or even
64 harmful.

65 **3. Sustainability dimensions of alternative proteins and future foods in** 66 **flexitarian diets**

67 The prescriptive role of AP-FF products (which can be animal-, plant-, or cell- based) in future
68 flexitarian diets is undefined because they are novel items and tradeoffs amongst sustainability
69 dimensions must be considered. We chose four sustainability dimensions (i.e., environment,
70 nutrition/health, animal welfare, and antibiotic overuse) because of their influence on dietary change.
71 The main driver of incorporating AP-FF into future flexitarian diets stems from their potential to have
72 lower environmental impacts than contemporary animal-sourced foods (C-ASF), which we define as
73 conventionally produced land- and sea- based meat (e.g., livestock, seafood). C-ASF, on average, have
74 much higher environmental impacts than contemporary plant-sourced foods (C-PSF). Antibiotic use
75 and animal welfare are other areas in which C-PSF have a distinct advantage. Thus, to be a
76 competitive substitute, AP-FF should have lower antibiotic use and animal welfare burdens than C-
77 ASF and should ideally be close to those of C-PSF. When the nutrition/health dimension is
78 considered, the line between the role of various food products within diets becomes less clear. In

79 particular, many argue to include small amounts of C-ASF to ensure nutrient adequacy is met.
80 Consequently, it is imperative that AP-FF nutritionally match or out-match C-ASF. As AP-FF
81 products exist in various degrees across these four sustainability dimensions, the following sections
82 detail the sustainability of AP-FF in relation to C-ASF and, when data is available, to C-PSF. To date,
83 the role of AP-FF in flexitarian diets has not been holistically quantified. Consequently, we
84 predominantly focus on AP-FF food products.

85 **3.1 Nutrition and health**

86 A benefit of flexitarian diets is their ability to incorporate C-ASF foods as a source of bioavailable
87 nutrients in small enough portions that certain health risks associated with C-ASF are lessened when
88 compared to status quo diets. Thus, AP-FF should contribute to flexitarian diets in a similar manner-
89 meaning they can provide nutrients that C-PSF cannot with minimized environmental risks. The
90 following section illustrates key issues of consideration related to nutrient deficiencies, nutrient
91 bioavailability, and nutritional equivalency claims between AP-FF and C-ASF, as well as allergens,
92 food safety, and ultra-processing concerns surrounding AP-FF.

93 Micronutrient deficiencies are a global issue even for wealthier sub-populations; deficiencies are of
94 particular concern in lower-income regions and for children because they have specific growth
95 requirements (Grace et al., 2018). More common examples of deficiencies relevant to traditional plant-
96 based diets include iron, calcium, zinc, riboflavin, vitamin D, vitamin B-12, and fatty acids such as
97 eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) (Craig, 2009; Saunders et al., 2013;
98 Springmann et al., 2018a; WHO, 2021). Limited modelling studies on the incorporation of AP-FF into
99 diets exist; however, a recent study found that partial substitution of C-ASF for plant-based meat led
100 to decreases in zinc, protein, and vitamin B-12 but also to increases in polyunsaturated fats, folate, and
101 fiber (Vatanparast et al., 2020). Another study found increases in sugar, salt, and carbohydrates with
102 decreases in protein, iron, and vitamin B-12; however, it also found increases in fiber and decreases in
103 saturated fat intake (Farsi et al., 2021). Insects, fungi, and microalgae, are nutrient-dense in pertinent
104 nutrients such as protein, fatty acids, iron, vitamin A, and vitamin B-12 (Caporgno & Mathys, 2018;
105 Parodi et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2019). Vitamin supplements can mitigate deficiencies; however,
106 limited studies exist that explore their bioavailability and potential environmental impacts. While the
107 inclusion of C-ASF may circumvent nutrient inadequacies more easily, some, like processed meat, can
108 be associated with dietary diseases such as coronary heart disease and colorectal cancer. Accordingly,
109 for AP-FF to be competitive, they must be close to the beneficial nutritional value of C-ASF with a
110 minimized risk of associated health concerns. While microalgae are assumed to have positive health
111 benefits because of their fatty acid profile (Adarme-Vega et al., 2012); in general, few robust studies
112 on AP-FF and human health exist.

113 Bioaccessibility, bioavailability, and bioactivity, which collectively measure how the body absorbs
114 and utilizes nutrients, pose additional complexity because of knowledge gaps. For example,
115 antinutrients such as phytates, oxalates, and lectins, commonly found in legumes, leafy vegetables, and
116 grains, can block mineral absorption. The relationship between AP-FF and antinutrients and their role
117 in human health is still poorly understood (Parodi et al., 2018). Additionally, protein quality is of

118 particular concern for vegan and vegetarian diets because C-ASF are more complete sources of amino
119 acids with a higher digestibility. While plant sources can be combined to meet requirements, planning
120 requires knowledge and time. Amino acids (e.g., lysine, methionine, threonine, and tryptophan) exist
121 in AP-FF (Ru et al., 2020; Tang et al., 2019), but their quantity in relation to C-ASF varies. For
122 microalgae, one study found that while protein bioaccessibility was high, fatty acid bioaccessibility
123 was very low, and that novel processing treatments might increase this percentage (Canelli et al.,
124 2020).

125 Plant-based and cultured meat products are formulated to match the nutritional value of C-ASF.
126 However, a recent study found that while nutritional labels were equivalent, when comparing grass-fed
127 beef to plant-based alternatives, the overall metabolic profiles varied up to 90 percent (van Vliet et al.,
128 2021). This lack of nutritional equivalency is relevant because these metabolites, which include
129 antioxidants, fatty acids, phenols, etc, are associated with anti-inflammatory and immunological roles
130 in our body (van Vliet et al., 2021). One study found that plant-based meat alternatives were often
131 higher in dietary fiber or refined carbohydrates and lower in cholesterol; surprisingly, the saturated fat
132 content of certain plant-based substitutes were comparable to meat (Bohrer, 2019) and other
133 assessment found that protein, zinc, and vitamin B12 can be lower in certain beef alternatives
134 (Harnack et al., 2021). On the other hand, certain plant-based substitutes are formulated to have lower
135 saturated and trans fat contents than meat (Lichtenstein & Food Frontier, 2020). Such a variation in
136 outcomes is unsurprising because there are no fortification standards for plant-based alternatives. In
137 fact, a recent study found that plant-based milk beverages also had significant variations in nutrient
138 contents (Drewnowski, 2021). Lastly, plant-based substitutes often incorporate additives to stabilize
139 the mixtures. While the possible health effects of additives such as gums or methylcellulose are still
140 inconclusive (Bohrer, 2019), processing practices that enhance quality without unnecessary additives,
141 such as colorings or thickeners, should be explored because consumers desiring 'clean' food labels
142 will avoid these products. As cellular meat currently has quite limited commercial availability, there
143 are no studies to validate the claims of being nutritionally-equivalent to their C-ASF counterparts.
144 However, some companies declare cultured meat can be formulated without disqualifying nutrients
145 like saturated fat (Zaraska, 2013). Therefore, for cultured meat, the health concerns of C-ASF might be
146 removed and compared to plant-based meat, the risk of nutritional deficiencies could be minimized.

147 Lastly, food safety, allergies, and ultra-processing are of concern when comparing AP-FF to C-ASF
148 and C-PSF. Food safety risks are a health concern and a major barrier to adopting more sustainable
149 feed substrates for several AP-FF. As with C-ASF and C-PSF, there is a risk of microbial or chemical
150 contamination under mismanaged production. For example, there is a chance of heavy metal,
151 pesticide, or mycotoxin exposure in insects if their substrate is contaminated and for microalgae there
152 is a risk of heavy metal, toxin, or pesticide exposure (Spiegel et al., 2013). With respect to the second
153 point, food allergies are on the rise worldwide (Jones, 2020), and the potential for new allergen
154 pathways with the introduction of AP-FF should be explored. The impacts of ultra-processed foods on
155 diets are receiving more attention because the processing and formulation effects on the food matrix
156 can lead to a lower quality product, and recent studies argue that certain plant-based products might
157 fall into this category (Kraak, 2022; WHO, 2021).

158 3.2 Environment

159 The major benefit of AP-FF lies in their potential to have lower environmental impacts than C-ASF. A
160 debated tradeoff between AP-FF and C-ASF is that the adoption of certain AP-FF could lead to high
161 energy demands (and potentially high GHG emissions) but lower land use values. Other major
162 considerations include scalability and variability because AP-FF are novel and unoptimized products.
163 Sustainability outcomes can change when estimated at pilot-scale versus at economical-scales and
164 variability in environmental impacts for the same AP-FF product can be high due to differences in
165 production system parameters or species. Accordingly, the role of AP-FF in flexitarian diets while
166 respecting planetary boundaries is not fully clear.

167 The environmental impacts of cultured meat in relation to C-ASF is still debated. The impacts can
168 substantially vary depending on study parameters, production system, and C-ASF comparison product
169 (i.e., is cultured meat compared to chicken or beef). A more established consensus is on land use
170 which is generally lower for cultured meat, and this is of particular interest as an increasing population
171 relies on limited land. Production in vertically-grown bioreactors close to city centers reduces land use
172 requirements and transportation distance of the final product to consumers, however, not those of the
173 raw materials. For the GHG impact category, results vary. One study estimated that over a 1000-year
174 time frame, cultured meat could have higher or comparable impacts to beef (Lynch & Pierrehumbert,
175 2019). However, scenarios assumed limited decarbonization; as the promise of energy decoupling
176 increases, such an assumption might be unrealistic. Moreover, they used a novel GHG accounting
177 approach that treats methane more favorably than in carbon equivalent methods because they account
178 for temporal variations of the gases. Another study found that the combined impacts including climate
179 change and environmental human health (e.g., respiratory organics) were significantly higher for
180 cultured meat than chicken and dairy sources of protein (Smetana et al., 2015). When compared to
181 beef, one study ascertained that the impacts of cellular meat were lower with the exception of energy
182 use, which was slightly higher; they further asserted impacts varied according to the feed substrate
183 (i.e., cyanobacteria-fed cellular meat had lower impacts than crop-fed) (Tuomisto et al., 2014). A
184 recent report concluded that cultured meat is much more sustainable than chicken and beef (Sinke &
185 Odegard, 2021). This report claims to be the first LCA that uses actual company data; previous studies
186 used hypothetical data. Thus, as cultured meat production increases and better data becomes available
187 it might be that results will change from originally assumed.

188 As with cultured meat, on average, microalgae have low land use requirements but high energy
189 demands. Microalgae can be produced in fermenter systems in a confined warehouse space similar to
190 cultured meat or in outdoor ponds when proper climatic conditions are met. Many species of
191 microalgae exist that are fed myriad feeds and processed using different technologies either
192 heterotrophically, mixotrophically, or autotrophically. Thus, a fair amount of variation in
193 environmental outcomes exist. Environmental performance can be optimized by utilizing a food waste
194 substrate or residues (Smetana et al., 2017); moreover, organic substrates in heterotrophic and
195 mixotrophic cultivation lead to greater microalgae concentrations.

196 Insects generally have lower impacts than most C-ASF; although, their energy use can be comparable
197 (Halloran et al., 2017; Ooninx & Boer, 2012; Smetana et al., 2019). However, one study argues that

198 as production of insects scale, environmental impacts might be comparable to certain C-ASF like
199 chicken because of reductions in feed conversion efficiencies; this study focused on crickets and noted
200 that other species or alternative feeds might have more beneficial outcomes (Lundy & Parrella, 2015).
201 On the other hand, such an increase in environmental impacts with scale, for crickets, was not found in
202 other studies (Halloran et al., 2017). For C-PSF, one study compared insects against different plant-
203 based feeds and generally found higher impacts except in the case of land use (Smetana et al., 2019).
204 Overall, there is a fair amount of variability in environmental footprints due to the substrate used,
205 insect species, or production practice.

206 Due to the high energy usage of these AP-FF, the advent of wide-spread renewable energy would
207 make these systems much more competitive. However, production of certain renewable technologies
208 requires rare earth materials and land. The large differences in impact values across studies are not
209 unexpected because of differing system boundaries and low technology readiness levels that result in
210 unoptimized and high variations in inputs and production practices; accordingly, these AP-FF have not
211 fully benefited from economies of scale. For example, standardized cellular meat production is
212 hindered by scalability issues such as bioreactor type and cell production (Post et al., 2020).

213 The last two food groups include fungi-based products and plant-based meat. Limited sustainability
214 studies on mycoprotein exist. One study found comparable environmental impacts to that of chicken
215 on a ready-to-eat kg basis; however, on a digestible dry matter protein content basis, mycoprotein had
216 greater impacts than chicken (Smetana et al., 2015). Contrastingly, on a protein basis in another study,
217 mycoprotein had lower land use and GHG impacts than C-ASF, including chicken (Parodi et al.,
218 2018). The use of different functional units makes direct comparisons across these studies impractical.
219 As shown in different studies (Heller & Keoleian, 2018; Smetana et al., 2015), plant-based meat
220 alternatives often have better environmental profiles. The C-PSF primary materials have lower
221 footprints than C-ASF and processing impacts are relatively low.

222 **3.3 Animal welfare**

223 Diets that rely on C-ASF have significant animal welfare issues due to poor living standards and
224 abuse. For example, the fish market suffers from by-catch and land-based animals are often raised in
225 closed quarters with unsanitary conditions that can lead to zoonotic outbreaks. In theory, welfare
226 concerns can be mitigated by sourcing foods from trusted or certified farmers. Unfortunately, there
227 have been many cases in which certificate schemes are significantly less robust than advertised
228 (Michail, 2018). The issues of animal welfare concerning other AP-FF are less straightforward.
229 Researchers have shown that insects release hormones when exposed to stress but they found cooling
230 and then rapidly cutting the insect was a gentle killing method (Aarts et al., 2019). Arguably, the
231 reduction of stress or potential harm when compared to that of C-ASF is considerable. However, if
232 insects do perceive stress, then the fact that more insects must be killed to provide the same amount of
233 calories means that animal welfare issues will occur on a wider scale. For cultured meat, animal cells
234 are needed as bioreactor inputs, but it is possible for cultured beef or chicken production to remove
235 cells via biopsies with minimal harm. In addition to cell lines, animals may be needed for blood
236 serum; however, newer technologies can create cultured meat without the use of this (Domigan et al.,
237 2022). Plant-based substitutes generally have a minimal risk of animal welfare issues. However, some

238 vegetarian products may contain egg, which can have associated animal welfare and antibiotic use
239 issues (Rubio et al., 2020). Additionally, one study argues that plant-based meat can lead to habitat
240 destruction via monocultures and species endangerment (Rubio et al., 2020). However, more research
241 should be done to quantify monoculture destruction (e.g., insect loss and pesticide use) from plant-
242 based production systems versus animal systems that rely on large amounts of feed.

243 **3.4 Antibiotic overuse**

244 Plant-based products (i.e., microalgae, fungi, plant-based meat, and C-PSF) also have minimal risk of
245 antibiotic overuse. This issue is of concern in the meat industry due to antimicrobial resistance, which
246 is becoming a leading cause of death (Murray et al., 2022). The extent to which antibiotics are used in
247 cultured meat is unclear. Companies may use them to reduce contamination risk (Zaraska, 2013).
248 Contrastingly, some claim antibiotics are unnecessary (Post et al., 2020); however, this would require
249 the use of clean rooms. Lastly, it is possible for insects to be contaminated with antibiotics, depending
250 on the feed used (Spiegel et al., 2013).

251 **4. The differentiated role of meat products (e.g., chicken vs. beef) in future** 252 **flexitarian diets**

253 Based on the current state of AP-FF technology levels as well as the limitations of C-PSF-only diets,
254 the incorporation of C-ASF can be justified in specific instances. In low-income countries (LIC) many
255 livelihoods are linked to livestock and eliminating these systems could lead to increased financial
256 insecurity particularly in rural areas via income loss and reductions in the ability to manage risk
257 (Banda & Tanganyika, 2021; FAO, 2009; Leroy et al., 2022). This would compound on the generally
258 low accessibility LIC have in terms of variety and amount of products that can substitute for meat.
259 Additionally, livestock elimination could result in more micronutrient deficiencies and associated
260 health consequences in these regions (FAO, 2009; Leroy et al., 2022; Nordhagen et al., 2020).
261 Moreover, increasing non-livestock production and expanding trade to diversify food supply can be
262 financially prohibitive to certain farmers, industries, and governments; it can also be impractical
263 because certain lands are unsuitable for crops but can be used for raising livestock. Furthermore,
264 particular agricultural systems have evolved to sustainably incorporate both animals and crops (e.g.,
265 mixed-livestock cropping systems wherein animals consume waste, provide manure for fertilizer, or
266 control weeds) (FAO, 2009; van Zanten et al., 2016). Moreover, at the global scale, meat consumption
267 is increasing and is expected to grow by 14% by 2030 (OECD/FAO, 2021). Thus, it is important to
268 consider differences between meat products when defining flexitarian diets, and, more research should
269 be conducted to see how other meat products can substitute for environmentally-impacting ruminant
270 animals, particularly when considering nutritional (e.g., bioavailability), environmental, animal
271 welfare, livelihood, and circularity tradeoffs.

272 Future studies should focus on quantifying the aforementioned tradeoffs to determine where certain
273 types of animals are needed. Even when considering regional differences, of the major meat products,
274 beef, on average, has higher impacts followed by goat and sheep meat, pig meat, and poultry (Green et
275 al., 2021; Poore & Nemecek, 2018a); ruminants are significant sources of methane emissions (Poore

276 & Nemecek, 2018b), which can be over 80x more damaging than CO₂ over a 20-year period, and the
277 recent IPCC report states one of the fastest pathways to reduce negative climatic impacts is by
278 decreasing methane emissions (IPCC, 2021). On the other hand, one study found that beef was the
279 most nutrient dense followed by goat and sheep, poultry, and pig meat (Green et al., 2021); however,
280 the higher saturated fat content of beef is often associated with worsened health outcomes. This issue
281 of nutrition is further complicated by bioaccessibility, bioavailability, and bioactivity. For example,
282 iron has two forms: heme and nonheme; humans are more adept at absorbing the former, which
283 predominately comes from animals. Moreover, the percentage of heme iron varies across products,
284 with beef generally having higher levels than pork and chicken (Cross et al., 2012). Seafood can have
285 comparable or lower environmental impacts when compared to livestock. In particular, bivalves have
286 overall lower environmental impacts compared to other seafood (Gephart et al., 2021). Nevertheless,
287 impacts that are harder to quantify like biodiversity loss and ecosystem collapse remain of significant
288 concern for this food group. With regards to nutrition, seafood is seen as beneficial due to their
289 polyunsaturated fat content and overall health benefits (Harvard, 2018; Hoekstra et al., 2013). With
290 respect to animal welfare, smaller animals like less-environmentally impacting chickens will have to
291 be killed in much larger numbers to feed the same number of people as one cow. Examination of
292 livelihood concerns reveals that larger livestock provides supplementary benefits such as plowing and
293 transport and are integrated into national economic structures by providing by-products (Banda &
294 Tanganyika, 2021).

295 The consumption of C-ASF also relates to the circularity perspective, and a stricter consideration of
296 this could reveal new tradeoffs. For example, if certain populations, like those in higher-income
297 nations, consuming underutilized animal parts (e.g., liver, feet), on a larger scale, could likely address
298 more nutrient deficiencies with lower amounts of animals and associated environmental costs. As one
299 study found, offals can be high in key micronutrients (Ortenzi & Beal, 2021). However, in many
300 regions, the adoption of offals would require overcoming consumer hesitance and learning how to
301 prepare these. A recent paper did quantify this perspective and found that in a circular system, it was
302 more environmentally friendly to produce foods such as pork and beef from dairy cows as opposed to
303 poultry, in part because they are better at converting low quality feeds (van Selm et al., 2022).

304 **5. Production-based interventions for shaping sustainable flexitarian diets**

305 While behavior choice of individual consumers is important, production-based interventions that
306 increase nutrient contents, in instances of deficiencies, while minimizing environmental impacts will
307 be crucial in meeting future sustainability goals. Nutrition-sensitive food production is needed because
308 deficiencies are increasing [e.g., iron and iodine for women (GBD, 2021)]; additionally, climate
309 change is altering nutritional contents of staple foods like legumes and grains by reducing protein,
310 zinc, and iron concentrations (Myers et al., 2014), and, in general, nutritional profiles of the same food
311 item can vary due to soil conditions, changes in agricultural management and processing practices,
312 genetics, or feed compositions (Green et al., 2020). Specific examples of such production-oriented
313 interventions include (i) novel processing practices like pulsed electric field processing to increase
314 bioaccessibility in AP-FF without destroying nutrient stability; (ii) integrating seaweed into cow feed
315 to reduce methane emissions by over 80% (Roque et al., 2021) which may also be nutritional benefits

316 as microalgae feed supplementation can improve the fatty acid content of animal products (Saadaoui et
317 al., 2021); (iii) or targeted fortification of foods, including AP-FF, that have lower-environmental
318 impacts to meet nutrient requirements. While these dimensions are key, production must also consider
319 cultural acceptance and organoleptic properties such as taste, and texture; production examples include
320 high moisture extrusion for fibril AP-FF and heterotrophically or mixotrophically cultivated
321 microalgae to overcome the green color of final products.

322 Resilient systems are needed in the face of climate change, and AP-FF are generally less susceptible to
323 agricultural shocks (with the exception of their feed or primary material). Crops yields suffer from
324 pests, disease, freezing, high winds, and drought, while disease can necessitate animal culling. AP-FF,
325 on average, have lower resilience risks because of their closed and thus more controlled environments
326 in addition to their modular design capabilities and decentralized networks; moreover, adoption of AP-
327 FF can support a resilient food system through diversification (Tzachor et al., 2021). This is pertinent
328 as the concept of dietary diversification is increasingly explored in agri-food production systems
329 (Bogard et al., 2018; Green et al., 2021).

330 **6. The importance of context-specific boundaries**

331 The sustainability of a product or diet differs depending on context-specific situations that dictate what
332 is feasible in a certain area or for a certain person, based on boundary constraints. More and more,
333 studies recognize the importance of contextual dependence when devising sustainable food systems
334 (Barrett et al., 2020). We define five categories of context-specific boundaries: namely, environmental,
335 access, nutritional, knowledge, and cultural boundaries. Figure 1 is a conceptualization of how the role
336 of AP-FF, C-ASF, and C-PSF in flexitarian diets is affected by context-dependent boundaries.

337 Environmental boundaries vary based on local resources and emissions, a common example is
338 avoiding water-intensive production in water-scarce regions; nuts, for example, can function as a meat
339 substitute on a GHG and nutritional basis but not on a water basis. Relatedly, consumers should avoid
340 products with high environmental footprints due to air-transportation or out-of-season produce from
341 greenhouses with inefficient lighting, insulation, or irrigation. Moreover, dietary recommendations
342 that suggest increasing vegetable or fruit consumption ignore the fact that certain foods can have
343 markedly different impacts than others in the same group and that sustainability can vary depending
344 on season. For example, globally, greenhouse gas emissions of berries and tomatoes are much higher
345 than other fruits and vegetables, particularly when grown in greenhouses (Poore & Nemecek, 2018b).
346 Despite such variations, it is important to reiterate that plant-based foods, on average, have much
347 lower impacts than A-SF. Such concerns will also be relevant for AP-FF, with the possible exception
348 of seasonality as AP-FF can be grown in controlled environments. For example, the use of a food loss
349 or waste substrate would lead to a lower environmental footprint for insects and microalgae; however,
350 for insects consumed by humans, food waste is not approved as a feed source in several regions like
351 the EU. The applicability of cellular agriculture (i.e., microalgae and cultured meat) in lower-income

352 countries could be limited due to a lack of renewable energy capacity and associated capital
353 expenditures needs.

354 Monetary and physical access is another major boundary constraint. Areas with restricted food access
355 are known as ‘food deserts’ and can exist in varying degrees of severity across economic regions.
356 Many rural areas or marginalized urban communities only have access to a limited amount and variety
357 of fruits or vegetables and protein-rich alternatives such as lentils or tofu. Furthermore, AP-FF are
358 predominantly available in wealthier communities. Physical access, moreover, to these foods, does not
359 guarantee affordability. One study found that the universal EAT-Lancet diet was unaffordable to over
360 1.58 billion consumers (Hirvonen et al., 2020b), and plant-based meat is more expensive than their C-
361 ASF counterparts (Rubio et al., 2020). Current subsidies greatly favor C-ASF, if subsidies were to
362 shift to more plant-based products then the unaffordability issue could be partially solved.

363 Nutritional boundaries vary depending on personal or regional needs; currently, however, these are not
364 sufficiently considered. In addition to general diet deficiencies, the severity of them can vary by
365 locality because food items can have different nutritional profiles; for example, wheat has varying
366 levels of protein, and even within countries the micronutrient content of cereals can vary depending on
367 soil conditions (Gashu et al., 2021); moreover, differences in regional management or cooking
368 practices affect nutritional profiles (Green et al., 2020). The dietary intake requirements of people also
369 differ according to weight, gender, age, and physical activity. One example is the higher deficiencies
370 of iron in women than men. In such instances, women likely need to consume products with more
371 bioavailable forms of iron; thus, recommendations should consider bioavailability and not just the
372 nutrient amount of a food item. Researchers are now beginning to delve deeper into personalized
373 nutrition; however, there are still many gaps in this area (Herrero et al., 2021). For AP-FF it is possible
374 they are more tailorable to personal nutrition goals, making their role in future flexitarian diets more
375 pronounced.

376 Cultural acceptance boundaries are much harder to address, but nonetheless important. One could
377 devise the ‘most’ sustainable food product or dietary pattern, and people would likely reject it based
378 on cultural preference, lifestyle compromises, or politics. Consequently, aligning with consumer habits
379 and preferences is essential. For example, meat consumption in lower-middle and upper-middle
380 income countries increases every year with rising wealth, partially driven by meat being a ‘status-
381 symbol.’ Additionally, certain consumer groups might be hesitant to consume insects and cultured
382 meat due to disgust or unnaturalness, respectively (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017) and aversions to
383 processed foods, such as extruded plant products for meat replacements, may also play a role when
384 consumers select foods (Hartmann et al., 2022).

385 Finally, the knowledge boundary is defined as a lack of knowledge or data that prevents sustainable
386 consumer choices. For behavioral choice to be effective, the public needs more complete data on
387 products, and this information should be equitably distributed because lower-income populations may
388 have less access to knowledge regarding the consumption of more sustainable diets; additionally,
389 when information is available it may not be communicated effectively with labelling. A consumer can
390 try to avoid nuts grown in water-scarce regions or out-of-season foods produced in inefficient

391 greenhouses, but a lack of accessible trade data and incomplete food labelling restricts a consumer's
392 ability to determine a product's origin and production conditions. In theory, one could strive to include
393 a sufficient amount of lower-impact food items to compensate for those of a higher impact. This,
394 however, remains difficult because the environmental impacts of a single food item can vary up to 50-
395 fold (Poore & Nemecek, 2018b). This is likely even more true for AP-FF products that exhibit a lower
396 technology-readiness level with high variations in outcomes. Labelling is also an issue with animal
397 welfare; for instance, 'free-range' eggs or chicken do not always mean these animals had a cruelty free
398 life.

399 **7. Discussion and outlook**

400 Overall, AP-FF must have nutritional profiles that are equivalent to or better than C-ASF (while
401 accounting for bioavailability concerns), better health outcomes, and lower environmental impacts.
402 AP-FF should also have lower animal welfare and antibiotic use burdens. Currently, there is a large
403 variability in nutritional compositions of AP-FF and strong variations in production practices and
404 scaling issues lead to greatly different environmental outcomes (for better or for worse). Lastly, future
405 flexitarian diets should be based not only on behavioral change but also on sustainable production-
406 oriented interventions, and the integration of AP-FF into flexitarian diets should abide by context-
407 specific boundaries of access, knowledge, environment, nutrition, and culture.

408 The role of AP-FF in flexitarian diets is variable. Plant-based meat has low environmental impacts, but
409 nutritional contents can vary substantially leading to higher intakes of both disqualifying (e.g.,
410 saturated fat) and qualifying nutrients (e.g., fiber). Insects are promising because they generally have a
411 favorable nutritional profile and, on average, lower overall environmental impacts compared to C-
412 ASF. Animal welfare gains for insects, however, are more unclear. Conversely, while microalgae and
413 cultured meat also have promising nutritional benefits, the generally high energy demands (depending
414 on their production type—e.g., substrate used) means that further optimization, to overcome their
415 lower technology readiness levels, is needed to be competitive. Fermentation-based production, as
416 used with fungi, is receiving increased attention and funding; however, limited sustainability
417 assessments exist, which constricts our ability to assess their role in future flexitarian diets. For meat
418 replacements, there is an open question of which plant-based meat replacements industry should focus
419 on. For example, chicken is commonly replicated for consumers; however, the difference in
420 environmental impacts between plant-based substitutes and chicken is much smaller than with beef.
421 On the other hand, even if there are comparatively limited environmental gains with replacing chicken
422 production there are significant gains in terms of reduced animal welfare harm and antibiotic use;
423 additionally, globally, we consume much more chicken than beef. Finally, producers can focus on
424 hybrid-production to advance faster adoption of AP-FF such as the aforementioned cultured chicken
425 formulated with plant-protein because it is challenging to replicate meat with 100% cultured meat;
426 moreover, as already done, companies can formulate products with microalgae and insects to improve
427 nutritional profiles.

428 With respect to the environmental dimension, as mentioned, for some AP-FF (i.e., microalgae and
429 cultured meat) there is a big tradeoff because AP-FF adoption can lead to energy demands but low

430 land use. The use of renewable energy can provide massive gains for AP-FF, potentially more so than
431 C-ASF- This is because C-ASF have associated emissions such as biogenic methane (Johnson et al.,
432 2007) that cannot be mitigated with renewable technology. However, it is possible that certain areas
433 may not have sufficient renewable energy capacity for AP-FF. For example, installed renewable
434 energy capacity (MW) for Africa is projected to be between 50-80% in 2030, depending on the
435 scenario (KfW et al., 2020). Regardless, we need to investigate alternative processing for microalgae
436 and cultured meat that use less energy because, for example, solar power might require photovoltaic
437 cells that rely on rare earth minerals, and if significant solar energy is needed rooftops will be
438 insufficient and land will be needed. On the other hand, new technologies are being explored such as
439 agrivoltaics in which crops are grown under solar cells— such systems could help alleviate land use
440 pressure and have an added benefit of enhancing crop productivity (Barron-Gafford et al., 2019). As
441 population growth places a strain on finite arable land resources, we will need products like AP-FF
442 that use less land.. Despite the low land use, AP-FF still require land for substrate production unless
443 they are fed on low input substrates like residues or food loss and waste for insects and microalgae or
444 cyanobacteria for cultured meat. This not only confers environmental impact benefits for the food
445 product but it also contributes to a circular society. Feed or substrates, however, in addition to
446 affecting nutritional profiles, can also influence final product yields and indirectly environmental
447 impacts; thus, these tradeoffs should be examined in more detail.

448 With respect to the other sustainability dimensions, for nutrition and health, future work should focus
449 on the nutritional equivalency claims of alternative products and how differences in potential health
450 outcomes could arise from replacing meat products with AP-FF by changing nutrient profiles or
451 introducing new allergens. As mentioned, plant-based substitutes can still contain high levels of
452 saturated fat, sugars, and sodium, and AP-FF may not have bioavailable forms of key nutrients; on the
453 other hand, plant-based meat confers fiber and other beneficial micronutrients, single-cell technologies
454 such as microalgae, yeast, or bacteria, are thought to have beneficial nutritional profiles, and cultured
455 meat has the potential to improve fatty acid profiles and reduce associated health risks. Moreover,
456 careful attention should be paid to processing and formulation with an aim to avoid plant-based
457 products that could be classified as ultra-processed. Additionally, more long-term human studies
458 should be conducted with AP-FF. The role of access and potential restrictions in food sovereignty
459 with the addition of AP-FF that are centrally produced by large multinationals should be considered.
460 Finally, animal welfare and antibiotic use have promise to be highly reduced and their associated
461 effects greatly mitigated with the introduction of AP-FF, even with the consumption of insects and
462 cultured meat.

463 Looking forward, we will need policy and specific initiatives to achieve the goals set forth in this
464 commentary. Large scale database initiatives reflective of soil profiling, (bio)fortification,
465 management interventions, and alternative processing to understand regionalized differences in
466 nutritional and environmental profiles of the same food item and foods within the same group will
467 allow for the inclusion of more context-specific boundaries. For sustainability assessments, we need
468 more robust and standardized methods in combined sustainability analyses (Chaudhary et al., 2018;
469 Green et al., 2021; Springmann et al., 2018b; Willett et al., 2019). Within life cycle assessment, we
470 further need a more streamlined approach to using different functional units (i.e., nutrient- vs. mass-

471 based) and system boundaries because they confer noncomparable and variable sustainability results
472 across studies. There are still many gaps and limitations in defining a sustainable flexitarian diet in
473 relation to AP-FF and how this group compares to C-ASF and C-PSF as well as the existence of
474 tradeoffs between sustainability dimensions of these food groups. Gaps include assessing more
475 environmental footprints to avoid optimizing one at the expense of another, context-dependent
476 constraints like culture, access, and knowledge gaps, and assessments of changing nutritional profiles
477 with dietary substitution; despite these limitations, we hope that considering the points raised in this
478 commentary is of use.

Accepted

Credit authorship contribution statement

Ashley Green: Conceptualization, Writing- Original Draft, Writing- Review and Editing, Visualization. Christoph Blattmann: Writing- Review and Editing. Canxi Chen: Writing- Review and Editing. Alexander Mathys: Conceptualization, Writing- Review and Editing, Visualization.

Declaration of interest: Declarations of interest: none.

Funding: This research was partially supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 861976 project SUSustainable INsect CHAIN (H2020 SUSINCHAIN) and partially funded by the National Research Program "Sustainable Economy: resource-friendly, future-oriented, innovative" (NRP 73) by the Swiss National Science Foundation (Grant number: [407340_172415](#)).

Accepted

8. References

- Aarts, K. W. P., De, M. C. M., Jacobs, A. L. M., Jansen, M. P. M., Mathys, A., Mescher, M. C., & Prentner, R. (2019). *Processing of Insect Larvae* (Patent No. WO2019234106A1).
- Adarme-Vega, T. C., Lim, D. K. Y., Timmins, M., Vernen, F., Li, Y., & Schenk, P. M. (2012). Microalgal biofactories: a promising approach towards sustainable omega-3 fatty acid production. *Microbial Cell Factories*, *11*, 96. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1475-2859-11-96>
- Banda, L. J., & Tanganyika, J. (2021). Livestock provide more than food in smallholder production systems of developing countries. *Animal Frontiers*, *11*(2), 7–14. <https://doi.org/10.1093/af/vfab001>
- Barrett, C. B., Benton, T. G., Cooper, K. A., Fanzo, J., Gandhi, R., Herrero, M., James, S., Kahn, M., Mason-D’Croz, D., Mathys, A., Nelson, R. J., Shen, J., Thornton, P., Bageant, E., Fan, S., Mude, A. G., Sibanda, L. M., & Wood, S. (2020). Bundling innovations to transform agri-food systems. *Nature Sustainability*, *3*(12), 974–976. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-00661-8>
- Barron-Gafford, G. A., Pavao-Zuckerman, M. A., Minor, R. L., Sutter, L. F., Barnett-Moreno, I., Blackett, D. T., Thompson, M., Dimond, K., Gerlak, A. K., Nabhan, G. P., & Macknick, J. E. (2019). Agrivoltaics provide mutual benefits across the food–energy–water nexus in drylands. *Nature Sustainability*, *2*(9), 848–855. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0364-5>
- Bogard, J. R., Marks, G. C., Wood, S., & Thilsted, S. H. (2018). Measuring nutritional quality of agricultural production systems: Application to fish production. *Global Food Security*, *16*, 54–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2017.09.004>
- Bohrer, B. (2019). An investigation of the formulation and nutritional composition of modern meat analogue products. *Food Science and Human Wellness*, *8*(4), 320–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fshw.2019.11.006>
- Canelli, G., Tarnutzer, C., Carpine, R., Neutsch, L., Bolten, C. J., Dionisi, F., & Mathys, A. (2020). Biochemical and Nutritional Evaluation of Chlorella and Auxenochlorella Biomasses Relevant for Food Application. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, *0*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2020.565996>
- Caporgno, M. P., & Mathys, A. (2018). Trends in Microalgae Incorporation Into Innovative Food Products With Potential Health Benefits. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, *5*, 58. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2018.00058>
- Chaudhary, A., Gustafson, D., & Mathys, A. (2018). Multi-indicator sustainability assessment of global food systems. *Nature Communications*, *9*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-03308-7>
- Clark, M. A., Domingo, N. G. G., Colgan, K., Thakrar, S. K., Tilman, D., Lynch, J., Azevedo, I. L., & Hill, J. D. (2020). Global food system emissions could preclude achieving the 1.5° and 2°C climate change targets. *Science*, *370*(6517), 705–708. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba7357>
- Craig, W. J. (2009). Health effects of vegan diets. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, *89*(5), 1627S–1633S. <https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.2009.26736N>
- Cross, A. J., Harnly, J. M., Ferrucci, L. M., Risch, A., Mayne, S. T., & Sinha, R. (2012). Developing a heme iron database for meats according to meat type, cooking method and doneness level. *Food and Nutrition Sciences*, *3*(7), 905–913. <https://doi.org/10.4236/fns.2012.37120>

- Dagevos, H. (2021). Finding flexitarians: Current studies on meat eaters and meat reducers. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 114, 530–539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2021.06.021>
- Dolgin, E. (2020). Will cell-based meat ever be a dinner staple? *Nature*, 588(7837), S64–S67. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-03448-1>
- Domigan, L. J., Feisst, V., & Ogilvie, O. J. (2022). Recipes for cultured meat. *Nature Food*, 3(1), 9–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00437-z>
- Drewnowski, A. (2021). Plant-based milk alternatives in the USDA Branded Food Products Database would benefit from nutrient density standards. *Nature Food*, 2(8), 567–569. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00334-5>
- FAO (Ed.). (2009). *Livestock in the balance*. FAO.
- Farsi, D. N., Uthumange, D., Munoz Munoz, J., & Commane, D. M. (2021). The nutritional impact of replacing dietary meat with meat alternatives in the UK: a modelling analysis using nationally representative data. *The British Journal of Nutrition*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007114521002750>
- Gashu, D., Nalivata, P. C., Amede, T., Ander, E. L., Bailey, E. H., Botoman, L., Chagumaira, C., Gameda, S., Haefele, S. M., Hailu, K., Joy, E. J. M., Kalimbara, A. A., Kumssa, D. B., Lark, R. M., Ligowe, I. S., McGrath, S. P., Milne, A. E., Mossa, A. W., Munthali, M., ... Broadley, M. R. (2021). The nutritional quality of cereals varies geospatially in Ethiopia and Malawi. *Nature*, 594(7861), 71–76. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03559-3>
- GBD. (2021). *Global Burden of Disease*. Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation. <http://www.healthdata.org/gbd/2019>
- Gephart, J. A., Henriksson, P. J. G., Parker, R. W. R., Shepon, A., Gorospe, K. D., Bergman, K., Eshel, G., Golden, C. D., Halpern, B. S., Hornborg, S., Jonell, M., Metian, M., Mifflin, K., Newton, R., Tyedmers, P., Zhang, W., Ziegler, F., & Troell, M. (2021). Environmental performance of blue foods. *Nature*, 597(7876), 360–365. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03889-2>
- Grace, D., Domínguez Salas, P., Alonso, S., Lannerstad, M., Muunda, E. M., Ngwili, N. M., Omar, A., Khan, M., & Otodo, E. (2018). *The influence of livestock-derived foods on nutrition during the first 1,000 days of life* [Report]. International Livestock Research Institute. <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/handle/10568/92907>
- Green, A., Nemecek, T., Chaudhary, A., & Mathys, A. (2020). Assessing nutritional, health, and environmental sustainability dimensions of agri-food production. *Global Food Security*, 26, 100406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2020.100406>
- Green, A., Nemecek, T., Smetana, S., & Mathys, A. (2021). Reconciling regionally-explicit nutritional needs with environmental protection by means of nutritional life cycle assessment. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 312, 127696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127696>
- Halloran, A., Hanboonsong, Y., Roos, N., & Bruun, S. (2017). Life cycle assessment of cricket farming in north-eastern Thailand. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 156, 83–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.04.017>
- Harnack, L., Mork, S., Valluri, S., Weber, C., Schmitz, K., Stevenson, J., & Pettit, J. (2021). Nutrient Composition of a Selection of Plant-Based Ground Beef Alternative Products Available in the United States. *Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics*, 121(12), 2401–2408.e12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jand.2021.05.002>
- Hartmann, C., Furtwaengler, P., & Siegrist, M. (2022). Consumers' evaluation of the environmental friendliness, healthiness and naturalness of meat, meat substitutes, and other protein-rich foods. *Food Quality and Preference*, 97, 104486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2021.104486>

- Hartmann, C., & Siegrist, M. (2017). Consumer perception and behaviour regarding sustainable protein consumption: A systematic review. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 61, 11–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2016.12.006>
- Harvard. (2018, May 18). *New AHA guidelines recommend eating fish twice a week to improve heart health*. News. <https://www.hsph.harvard.edu/news/hsph-in-the-news/seafood-eating-guidelines-heart-health/>
- Heller, M. C., & Keoleian, G. (2018). *Beyond Meat's Beyond Burger Life Cycle Assessment: A detailed comparison between a plant-based and an animal-based protein source*. University of Michigan. <https://css.umich.edu/publication/beyond-meats-beyond-burger-life-cycle-assessment-detailed-comparison-between-plant-based>
- Herrero, M., Thornton, P. K., Mason-D'Croz, D., Palmer, J., Bodirsky, B. L., Pradhan, P., Barrett, C. B., Benton, T. G., Hall, A., Pikaar, I., Bogard, J. R., Bonnett, G. D., Bryan, B. A., Campbell, B. M., Christensen, S., Clark, M., Fanzo, J., Godde, C. M., Jarvis, A., ... Rockström, J. (2021). Articulating the effect of food systems innovation on the Sustainable Development Goals. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 5(1), e50–e62. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(20\)30277-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(20)30277-1)
- Hirvonen, K., Bai, Y., Headey, D., & Masters, W. A. (2020a). Affordability of the EAT–Lancet reference diet: a global analysis. *The Lancet Global Health*, 8(1), e59–e66. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(19\)30447-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(19)30447-4)
- Hirvonen, K., Bai, Y., Headey, D., & Masters, W. A. (2020b). Affordability of the EAT–Lancet reference diet: a global analysis. *The Lancet Global Health*, 8(1), e59–e66. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(19\)30447-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(19)30447-4)
- Hoekstra, J., Hart, A., Owen, H., Zeilmaker, M., Bokkers, B., Thorgilsson, B., & Gunnlaugsdottir, H. (2013). Fish, contaminants and human health: Quantifying and weighing benefits and risks. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 54, 18–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2012.01.013>
- IPCC. (2021). *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press.
- Johnson, J. M.-F., Franzluebbbers, A. J., Weyers, S. L., & Reicosky, D. C. (2007). Agricultural opportunities to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions. *Environmental Pollution*, 150(1), 107–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2007.06.030>
- Jones, R. (2020). *Why food allergies are on the rise*. <https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20201023-food-allergies-why-nut-dairy-and-food-allergy-are-rising>
- KfW, GIZ, & IRENA. (2020). *The renewable energy transition in Africa*. https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2021/March/Renewable_Energy_Transition_Africa_2021.pdf
- Kraak, V. I. (2022). Perspective: Unpacking the Wicked Challenges for Alternative Proteins in the United States: Can Highly Processed Plant-Based and Cell-Cultured Food and Beverage Products Support Healthy and Sustainable Diets and Food Systems? *Advances in Nutrition*, 13(1), 38–47. <https://doi.org/10.1093/advances/nmab113>
- Leroy, F., Abraini, F., Beal, T., Dominguez-Salas, P., Gregorini, P., Manzano, P., Rowntree, J., & van Vliet, S. (2022). Animal board invited review: Animal source foods in healthy, sustainable, and ethical diets – An argument against drastic limitation of livestock in the food system. *Animal*, 16(3), 100457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.animal.2022.100457>
- Lichtenstein, T., & Food Frontier. (2020). *Plant-based meat: a healthier choice*. Food Frontier. <https://www.foodfrontier.org/wp->

content/uploads/dlm_uploads/2020/08/Plant-Based_Meat_A_Healthier_Choice-1.pdf#gf_2

- Lundy, M. E., & Parrella, M. P. (2015). Crickets Are Not a Free Lunch: Protein Capture from Scalable Organic Side-Streams via High-Density Populations of *Acheta domesticus*. *PLOS ONE*, *10*(4), e0118785. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0118785>
- Lynch, J., & Pierrehumbert, R. (2019). Climate Impacts of Cultured Meat and Beef Cattle. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, *3*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fsufs.2019.00005>
- Malek, L., & Umberger, W. J. (2021). How flexible are flexitarians? Examining diversity in dietary patterns, motivations and future intentions. *Cleaner and Responsible Consumption*, *3*, 100038. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clrc.2021.100038>
- Michail, N. (2018). *Certification schemes are holding back true sustainability, says report*. FoodNavigator. <https://www.foodnavigator.com/Article/2018/05/03/Certification-schemes-are-holding-back-true-sustainability-says-report>
- Morach, B., Witte, B., Walker, D., von Koeller, E., Grosse-Holz, F., Rogg, J., Brigl, M., Dehnert, N., Obloj, P., Koktenturk, S., & Schulze, U. (2021, June 1). Food for Thought: The Protein Transformation. *Boston Consulting Group*. <https://www.bcg.com/en-ch/publications/2021/the-benefits-of-plant-based-meats>
- Murray, C. J., Ikuta, K. S., Sharara, F., Swetschinski, L., Aguilar, G. R., Gray, A., Han, C., Bisignano, C., Rao, P., Wool, E., Johnson, S. C., Browne, A. J., Chipeta, M. G., Fell, F., Hackett, S., Haines-Woodhouse, G., Hamadani, B. H. K., Kumaran, E. A. P., McManigal, B., ... Naghavi, M. (2022). Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis. *The Lancet*, *399*(10325), 629–655. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)02724-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)02724-0)
- Myers, S. S., Zanutti, A., Kloog, I., Huybers, P., Leakey, A. D. B., Bloom, A. J., Carlisle, E., Dieterich, L. H., Fitzgerald, G., Hasegawa, T., Holbrook, N. M., Nelson, R. L., Ottman, M. J., Raboy, V., Sakai, H., Sartor, K. A., Schwartz, J., Seneweera, S., Tausz, M., & Usui, Y. (2014). Increasing CO₂ threatens human nutrition. *Nature*, *510*(7503), 139–142. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13179>
- Nordhagen, S., Beal, T., & Haddad, L. (2020). *The role of animal-source foods in healthy, sustainable, and equitable food systems*. Global Alliance for Improved Nutrition. <https://www.gainhealth.org/sites/default/files/publications/documents/gain-discussion-paper-series-5-the-role-of-animal-source-foods-in-healthy-sustainable-and-equitable-food-systems.pdf>
- OECD/FAO. (2021). *OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2021-2030*. OECD Publishing. <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/cf68bf79-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/cf68bf79-en>
- Oonincx, D. G. A. B., & Boer, I. J. M. de. (2012). Environmental Impact of the Production of Mealworms as a Protein Source for Humans – A Life Cycle Assessment. *PLOS ONE*, *7*(12), e51145. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0051145>
- Ortenzi, F., & Beal, T. (2021). Priority Micronutrient Density of Foods for Complementary Feeding of Young Children (6–23 Months) in South and Southeast Asia. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, *8*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fnut.2021.785227>
- Parodi, A., Leip, A., De Boer, I. J. M., Slegers, P. M., Ziegler, F., Temme, E. H. M., Herrero, M., Tuomisto, H., Valin, H., Van Middelaar, C. E., Van Loon, J. J. A., & Van Zanten, H. H. E. (2018). The potential of future foods for sustainable and healthy diets. *Nature Sustainability*, *1*(12), 782–789. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0189-7>
- Poore, J., & Nemecek, T. (2018a). Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. *Science*, *360*(6392), 987–992. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag0216>
- Poore, J., & Nemecek, T. (2018b). Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. *Science*, *360*(6392), 987–992. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag0216>

- Post, M. J., Levenberg, S., Kaplan, D. L., Genovese, N., Fu, J., Bryant, C. J., Negowetti, N., Verzijden, K., & Moutsatsou, P. (2020). Scientific, sustainability and regulatory challenges of cultured meat. *Nature Food*, *1*(7), 403–415.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-020-0112-z>
- Roque, B. M., Venegas, M., Kinley, R. D., Nys, R. de, Duarte, T. L., Yang, X., & Kebreab, E. (2021). Red seaweed (*Asparagopsis taxiformis*) supplementation reduces enteric methane by over 80 percent in beef steers. *PLOS ONE*, *16*(3), e0247820.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0247820>
- Ru, I. T. K., Sung, Y. Y., Jusoh, M., Wahid, M. E. A., & Nagappan, T. (2020). *Chlorella vulgaris*: a perspective on its potential for combining high biomass with high value bioproducts. *Applied Phycology*, *1*(1), 2–11.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/26388081.2020.1715256>
- Rubio, N. R., Xiang, N., & Kaplan, D. L. (2020). Plant-based and cell-based approaches to meat production. *Nature Communications*, *11*(1), 6276.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20061-y>
- Saadaoui, I., Rasheed, R., Aguilar, A., Cherif, M., Al Jabri, H., Sayadi, S., & Manning, S. R. (2021). Microalgal-based feed: promising alternative feedstocks for livestock and poultry production. *Journal of Animal Science and Biotechnology*, *12*(1), 76.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40104-021-00593-z>
- Saunders, A. V., Davis, B. C., & Garg, M. L. (2013). Omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids and vegetarian diets. *Medical Journal of Australia*, *199*(S4), S22–S26.
<https://doi.org/10.5694/mja11.11507>
- Sinke, P., & Odegard, I. (2021). *LCA of cultivated meat*. https://cedelft.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2021/04/CE_Delft_190107_LCA_of_cultivated_meat_Def.pdf
- Smetana, S., Mathys, A., Knoch, A., & Heinz, V. (2015). Meat alternatives: life cycle assessment of most known meat substitutes. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, *20*(9), 1254–1267. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-015-0931-6>
- Smetana, S., Sandmann, M., Rohn, S., Pleissner, D., & Heinz, V. (2017). Autotrophic and heterotrophic microalgae and cyanobacteria cultivation for food and feed: life cycle assessment. *Bioresource Technology*, *245*, 162–170.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.08.113>
- Smetana, S., Schmitt, E., & Mathys, A. (2019). Sustainable use of *Hermetia illucens* insect biomass for feed and food: Attributional and consequential life cycle assessment. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, *144*, 285–296.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.01.042>
- Spiegel, M. van der, Noordam, M. Y., & Fels-Klerx, H. J. van der. (2013). Safety of Novel Protein Sources (Insects, Microalgae, Seaweed, Duckweed, and Rapeseed) and Legislative Aspects for Their Application in Food and Feed Production. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, *12*(6), 662–678.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12032>
- Springmann, M., Wiebe, K., Mason-D’Croz, D., Sulser, T. B., Rayner, M., & Scarborough, P. (2018a). Health and nutritional aspects of sustainable diet strategies and their association with environmental impacts: a global modelling analysis with country-level detail. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, *2*(10), e451–e461.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(18\)30206-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(18)30206-7)
- Springmann, M., Wiebe, K., Mason-D’Croz, D., Sulser, T. B., Rayner, M., & Scarborough, P. (2018b). Health and nutritional aspects of sustainable diet strategies and their association with environmental impacts: a global modelling analysis with country-level detail. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, *2*(10), e451–e461.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(18\)30206-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(18)30206-7)

- Tang, C., Yang, D., Liao, H., Sun, H., Liu, C., Wei, L., & Li, F. (2019). Edible insects as a food source: a review. *Food Production, Processing and Nutrition*, 1(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43014-019-0008-1>
- Tuninetti, M., Ridolfi, L., & Laio, F. (2022). Compliance with EAT–Lancet dietary guidelines would reduce global water footprint but increase it for 40% of the world population. *Nature Food*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00452-0>
- Tuomisto, H. L., Ellis, M. J., & Hastrup, P. (2014). Environmental impacts of cultured meat: alternative production scenarios. *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Life Cycle Assessment in the Agri-Food Sector*, 9.
- Tzachor, A., Richards, C. E., & Holt, L. (2021). Future foods for risk-resilient diets. *Nature Food*, 2(5), 326–329. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00269-x>
- Vaidyanathan, G. (2021). What humanity should eat to stay healthy and save the planet. *Nature*, 600(7887), 22–25. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-03565-5>
- van Selm, B., Frehner, A., de Boer, I. J. M., van Hal, O., Hijbeek, R., van Ittersum, M. K., Talsma, E. F., Lesschen, J. P., Hendriks, C. M. J., Herrero, M., & van Zanten, H. H. E. (2022). Circularity in animal production requires a change in the EAT-Lancet diet in Europe. *Nature Food*, 3(1), 66–73. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00425-3>
- van Vliet, S., Bain, J. R., Muehlbauer, M. J., Provenza, F. D., Kronberg, S. L., Pieper, C. F., & Huffman, K. M. (2021). A metabolomics comparison of plant-based meat and grass-fed meat indicates large nutritional differences despite comparable Nutrition Facts panels. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 13828. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-93100-3>
- van Zanten, H. H. E., Meerburg, B. G., Bikker, P., Herrero, M., & de Boer, I. J. M. (2016). Opinion paper: The role of livestock in a sustainable diet: a land-use perspective. *Animal*, 10(4), 547–549. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731115002694>
- Vatanparast, H., Islam, N., Shafiee, M., & Ramdath, D. D. (2020). Increasing Plant-Based Meat Alternatives and Decreasing Red and Processed Meat in the Diet Differentially Affect the Diet Quality and Nutrient Intakes of Canadians. *Nutrients*, 12(7), 2034. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12072034>
- WHO. (2021). *Plant-based diets and their impact on health, sustainability and the environment: a review of the evidence: WHO European Office for the Prevention and Control of Noncommunicable Diseases* (WHO/EURO:2021-4007-43766-61591). World Health Organization. Regional Office for Europe. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/349086>
- Willett, W., Rockström, J., Loken, B., Springmann, M., Lang, T., Vermeulen, S., Garnett, T., Tilman, D., DeClerck, F., Wood, A., Jonell, M., Clark, M., Gordon, L. J., Fanzo, J., Hawkes, C., Zurayk, R., Rivera, J. A., Vries, W. D., Sibanda, L. M., ... Murray, C. J. L. (2019). Food in the Anthropocene: the EAT–Lancet Commission on healthy diets from sustainable food systems. *The Lancet*, 393(10170), 447–492. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31788-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31788-4)
- Zaraska, M. (2013, August 19). *Is Lab-Grown Meat Good for Us?* The Atlantic. <https://www.theatlantic.com/health/archive/2013/08/is-lab-grown-meat-good-for-us/278778/>

Figure Caption

Fig 1. The role of context-specific boundaries in shaping future flexitarian diets. This figure represents the differentiated effect of context-specific boundaries on the role foods in sustainable flexitarian diets. Selected examples of specific boundaries within each category are provided.

Accepted

CONTEXT-SPECIFIC BOUNDARIES:

ENVIRONMENT: Environmental boundaries differ by region and environmental impacts of same food item/group can vary

- Regionally-explicit water scarcity
- Differentiated ability to adopt renewables
- Differences in production practices
- National regulatory approvals

ACCESS: Monetary and physical access vary based on locality and income level

- Food deserts
- Affordability

NUTRITION & HEALTH: Nutrient contents of a single food or food group can vary

- Regionally-explicit nutritional deficiencies
- Differences in production practices
- Gender-specific nutrient requirements

KNOWLEDGE: Information to support sustainable decision-making is lacking or unequally distributed

- Inaccessible trade data
- Incomplete food labelling
- Knowledge gaps linked to wealth and education

CULTURE: Consumer preference varies based on region

- Behavioral choice— e.g., politics, culture, lifestyle, disgust, naturalness